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● First record of *Perakianus hisamatsui* Nakane, 1963 (Coleoptera: Melandryidae: Melandryinae) from China

Shu-Lin YANG

School of Life Sciences, Guizhou Normal University, Universities Town, Huaxi District, Guiyang, Guizhou 550025, China;

 shulin.yang@outlook.com

Abstract: The genus *Perakianus* Pic, 1914 is newly recorded from China with the species, *Perakianus hisamatsui* Nakane, 1963, which was previously known only from Japan.

Keywords: false darkling beetle, Guiyang, Guizhou, Qianlingshan, taxonomy

● 中国长朽木甲科一新记录种——久松霹雳长朽木甲

杨书林

生命科学学院，贵州师范大学，贵州省贵安新区花溪大学城 550025，中国

摘要: 本文报道了我国长朽木甲科一新记录属种——久松霹雳长朽木甲 *Perakianus hisamatsui* Nakane, 1963, 该种之前仅分布于日本。

关键词: 长朽木甲，贵阳，贵州，黔灵山，分类

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● Introduction

The genus *Perakianus* (Coleoptera: Melandryidae: Melandryinae: Serropalpini) was established by Pic with the species *Perakianus atriceps* Pic, 1914 from Perak, Malaysia (Pic 1914). The genus exhibits a southeastern Palaearctic–Oriental distribution with six described species; however, the Nigerian species *Perakianus mullistriatus* Pic, 1933 does not belong to this genus (Nikitsky & Pollock 2010). Currently, *Perakianus hisamatsui* Nakane, 1963 has been recorded only from Japan. Based on specimens collected in Guiyang City, Guizhou Province, China, we report this species as new to the Chinese fauna. The habitus of the adult females is illustrated.

● Material and methods

Specimens of *P. hisamatsui* emerged from larvae in a piece of dead wood collected from Mount Qianling, Guiyang City. Morphological characters were examined using an Olympus SZ51 stereomicroscope. Habitus images were taken with a Canon EOS 5Ds digital camera equipped with a Canon MP-E 65 mm lens. The camera was mounted on a WeMacro focus rail for capturing images at different focus points. Focus stacking was performed using CombineZP. Specimens are deposited in the Insect Collection of the Laboratory of Zoology, School of Life Sciences, Guizhou Normal University, Guiyang, Guizhou, China (GZNULS).

FIGURE 1. Habitus of *Perakianus hisamatsui* Nakane, 1963, female: **a** dorsal view **b** ventral view. (Scale bar: 5 mm)

● **Taxonomy**

***Perakianus hisamatsui* Nakane, 1963 久松霹雳长朽木甲**

Perakianus hisamatsui Nakane, 1963: 223; **Type locality:** Kashima, Ehime, Shikoku, Japan.

Figs 1–3

Material examined: CHINA, Guizhou Province, Guiyang City, Yunyan District, Mount Qianling, February 23, 2025, larva in dead wood, emerged on June 14, 2025, leg. Yunxuan Yang and Shulin Yang. 1♀ (中国贵州省贵阳市黔灵山, 枯木中幼虫, 2025年2月23日采, 2025年6月14日羽化, 杨云瑄、杨书林采, 1♀); same data but emerged on June 29, 2025, 1♀ (采集信息同前, 但羽化日期为2025年6月29日).

FIGURE 2. Habitus of *Perakianus hisamatsui* Nakane, 1963, live female.

Diagnosis. Body (Figs 1, 2) length 13–13.5 mm, mostly black, head, prothorax, pro-coxae and part of meso-sternite reddish orange, maxillary palpi yellowish orange. Third to 10th antennomeres flattened and serrate, 11th fusiform. Pronotum parallel-sided with an impression on the middle of each side; a shallow middle groove present at basal half. Elytra as wide as prothorax, parallel sided, with each apex acuminate and obtusely rounded at apical 1/6; densely pubescent, transversely and irregularly strigose, the strigae rough and strong basally, gradually diminished posteriorly (Fig. 3a); each elytron with two or three weak longitudinal costae and a strong sutural carina, exhibiting a narrow strip between the sutural margin and the carina, with transverse rows of bristles in apical 2/3 of the strip (Fig. 3b). Outer sides of meso- and meta-tibiae with transverse rows of bristles (Fig. 3c).

Distribution. China (Guizhou); Japan.

Remarks. The large gap between the new locality and the type locality of *P. hisamatsui* suggests that the species is probably more widely distributed in southern China.

FIGURE 3. Habitus of *Perakianus hisamatsui* Nakane, 1963: **a** strigae on basal elytra **b** transverse rows of bristles on sutural margins of elytra **c** transverse rows of bristles on the outer side of left meso-tibia.

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● Additional information

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